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TEACHING VOCABULARY THROUGH MOVIES: AN EXPERIMENT

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Abstract: Aim of the study is to see how students build their Vocabulary effectively when teacher teach Vocabulary through movies. Hypotheses are to see that Vocabulary can be learnt well through movies. Students learn with enthusiasm. To see development in acquisitions of Vocabulary, Researcher experiments of teaching Vocabulary through movies on engineering students (GTU, Gujarat). Fifteen students were selected for the experimental group, and another 15 students of the same class were selected for a control group who were taught Vocabulary traditionally. Both groups were given Pre-Test, and Controlled group was taught Vocabulary traditionally, and Experimental group was taught Vocabulary through Movies. After this experiment, Researcher takes post-test to see the development of Vocabulary. Researcher finds that teaching Vocabulary through English movies is effective than the traditional way. The study concludes that students are interested when they are taught Vocabulary through movies. It shows that students learn Vocabulary faster when they are taught by movies.

Index Terms – Movie scene, Experimental group, controlled group, Vocabulary

Whatever we do, we try to have pleasure, if there is pleasure, work is done well, and same way students also want to have pleasure in class. Students have been tired of learning from traditional teaching methodology. Teaching through movies is an attempt to create pleasure in learning. Teaching vocabulary through movies removes the monotony of traditional teaching and creates pleasures in learning vocabulary with real context.

“Words have power to destroy and heal.
When words are true and kind they can change our world.”
- The Buddha.

Words of a language are just like bricks for constructing a building. Like bricks, they are vital for the building of a language. Language is made up of words. If we want to use language effectively, we must have a good stock of Vocabulary. “Vocabulary learning is an essential part in foreign language learning as the meanings of new words are very often emphasized, whether in books or in classrooms. It is also central to language teaching and is of paramount importance to a language learner.” (Alqahtani 21) If students want to communicate well, He or she has to use proper and useful words. Good Vocabulary is the ornament of communication. Language is electrified by words. “Vocabulary is fundamental to foreign language teaching because without adequate vocabulary students cannot not only express their own ideas but also comprehend others.” (Kuśnierek 6) The present study is an attempt to enrich English Vocabulary of students. Aim of the study is to see how students build their Vocabulary effectively when teacher teach Vocabulary through movies. In order to see development in acquisitions of Vocabulary, Researcher experiments of teaching Vocabulary through movies on engineering students. Fifteen students were selected for the experimental group, and another 15 students of the same class were selected for the control group who were taught Vocabulary traditionally. Vocabulary.com was used to take pre-test and post-test.

Both experimental and controlled group were given a pre-test to see the level of Vocabulary. Both were found A2 level of Vocabulary. The researcher selected few movies like Titanic, Jungle book, Lion king, Mogali, Aladdin, Planet of apps, Lucy, Harry porter, Pirates of Arabian, social network, Hangover, Hunger game, Toy story, cast away, Days of summer, Twilight, Break up, Forest Gump etc. The researcher uses these movies to teach Vocabulary for one month and take a test to see development. Here is a sample of exercise from movies
Researcher introduces movies Jungle book. Brief discussion takes place for story and themes.

The Researcher selects a particular scene of that movie and provides the following worksheet to every student. Before playing that scene, Researcher explains that students have watch the scene very carefully in order to understand vocabulary. Students have to match words with meaning. In Exercise (B) Students have to make sentences of same words

(A) Match the word with proper meaning from scene

(1) Shrieking:	(D) Escape from a place, person, or Situation.
(2) Panting:	(A) Feeling fear or anxiety; frightened.
(3) Roaring:	(B) Making high-pitched piercing cries or sounds.
(4) Stay away:	(F) breathing with short, quick breaths; out Of breath.
(5) Run away:	(C) making or uttering a roar
(6) Afriad:	(E) To not go near or become involved With someone.

1 _____ 2 _____ 3 _____ 4 _____ 5 _____ 6 _____

(B) Make your own sentences by using below words.

(1) Shrieking _____

(2) Panting _____

(3) Roaring _____

(4) Stay away _____

(5) Run away _____

(6) Afriad _____

Here there is one more sample of exercise. Titanic is a very famous movie. Most of the students have students have watched this movie. The Researcher selects the jumping scene of that movie and provides the following worksheet to every student. Before playing that scene, Researcher explains that students have to watch the movie scene very carefully in order to understand vocabulary. Students do as directed. These are words used in this clip.

(C) Fill gaps and make sentence of these words.

Example

(0) co__ (ld, ku hu) (Answer "Cold")

He like to drink cold water

1. Pre__me (su, ju, ka)

2. __stract (bi, dis, ti)

3. Unla__ (ce, ke, de)

4. Ab____ (kurd,surd,murd)

5. ____pellers (Pro, Pre,Pru)

After teaching one month, Researcher took post-test of an experimental and controlled group to evaluate the level of the vocabulary of students. It is understood better here blow chart.

Result

Controlled group of students were taught Vocabulary traditionally, and Researcher taught Vocabulary to experimental students through movies. Marks various between the controlled group and experimental group is seen clearly

Above chart of experimental group shows the development of student's percentage in the post-test. Marks of Pre-test and post-test is compared. Marks variation between pre-test and post-test seen. Mostly difference of 45 or 50 % is there. Percentage of Post-test is increased compared to the pre-test.

Chart of controlled group shows Various between Pre-test and post-test. It indicates development in post-test, but it is less compared to the Experimental group. So the result of the post-test of experimental and controlled group shows the development of a vocabulary of the experimental group. Researcher finds variation of two present in the experimental group after teaching English through movies. Researcher finds that teaching Vocabulary through English movies is effective than the traditional way. The study concludes that students are interested when they are taught Vocabulary through film. Students were observed excited by using films in the classroom. Teaching Vocabulary through movies provide real context to learn.

Students learn faster when the element of entertainment is added. Teaching Vocabulary through movies added entertainment factor in learning. Students of the 21st century are smarter than teachers in using technology. If technology is blended, then learning becomes active.

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